

VOCATIONAL CHOICE AND HEALTH PERCEPTION IN NURSING STUDENTS: A CROSS-SECTIONAL AND CORRELATIONAL STUDY

Gönül Kara Söylemez^{1*}, Emine Çubukcu²

Keywords

Health perception,

Nursing, Students,

Vocational choice

ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to determine the relationship between nursing students' vocational choice and health perception. This cross-sectional and correlational study was carried out with 308 nursing students. The study data were obtained by using the 'Student Introduction Form, the Vocational Choices in Entering Nursing Scale (VCENS) and the Health Perception Scale (HPS). Student nurses' VCENS total mean score is 55.59 ± 14.62 and HPS mean total is 50.67 ± 6.94 . In the study, a positive significant correlation was found between the VCENS total, Vocational Congruency subscale and Self-Awareness subscale ($p < 0.05$). In addition, a positive significant correlation was determined between the VCENS Total, Vocational Congruency, Survival Reasons subscales and the Importance of Health subscale ($p < 0.05$, $p < 0.001$). It was found that nursing students who thought that they were suitable for the vocation had higher self-awareness about their health and gave more importance to their health. It is recommended that vocational promotions and awareness activities should be organised for the correct perception of the vocation in the society.

INTRODUCTION

As there are factors that cause the emergence of every profession, the main factor in the emergence of the nursing profession is human needs. For this reason, the beginning of the nursing profession dates back to the existence of man¹. Nursing, which has constantly renew edit self with cultural, social and technological changes from past periods to the present, is an applied health discipline that deals with the health and well-being of individuals². The International Council of Nurses (ICN) defines nursing as 'the autonomous and co-operative care of individuals, families, groups and communities of all ages, sick or healthy, and in all settings. Nursing includes health promotion, disease prevention and care of the sick, disabled and dying. Advocacy, promotion of a safe environment, research, participation in shaping health policy and patient and health systems management, and education are so important nursing roles³.

Nursing is a professional profession with all these characteristics. Vocational choice is the orientation of individuals to wards the job that is suitable for their personality traits, abilities and satisfaction among many existing professions⁴. The choice of vocation is influenced by various factors such as family structure, environmental conditions, economic conditions and individual characteristics and constitutes one of the most important decisions in the lives of individuals. Choosing a vocation knowingly and willingly is associated with individuals being successful in their profession, fulfilling the roles and responsibilities required by the profession and ensuring continuity in the profession^{5,6}. Indifferent studies conducted with nurses and nursing students, significant relationships were reported between vocational choice and professional behaviour⁷, care behaviour⁸, and health perception⁵.

Health perception, defined as the evaluation of one's own health, is a concept related to the acquisition and maintenance of healthy lifestyle behaviours and health promotion⁵. With the acquisition of health-promoting behaviours, individuals can be protected from preventable diseases caused by lifestyle. Thus, it is thought that individuals who correctly evaluate and perceive their own

Volume: 3

Issue: 2

Page: 49– 58

Received: 23.03.2025

Accepted: 08.05.2025

Available online: 30.06.2025

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15701116

health will encounter fewer problems. It is among the main objectives of nursing education for nursing students to gain effective knowledge and skills in protecting and improving both their own and society's health⁹. It is reported that nursing students who adopt healthy lifestyle behaviours have better health perceptions¹⁰. When the literature was examined, it was determined that studies examining the relationship between nursing students' choice of vocation and health perception were limited⁵ and studies examining this relationship were needed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design and Sample

The research is a cross-sectional and correlational study. The study population consisted of 336 students studying in the Nursing Department of the Faculty of Health Sciences of a university in the 2024-2025 academic year. No sampling method was used in the study, and 308 students who met the inclusion criteria and attended classes on the data collection days were included in the study. The inclusion criteria for students were voluntary participation, age 18 years or older and studying in the nursing department. The exclusion criteria were refusal to participate and speech or hearing impairment. After the research was completed, a power analysis was performed to determine whether the sample size was sufficient. In this study, with a population size of 336 people, a minimum of 180 participants was determined to be necessary based on a sample calculation made assuming a 95% confidence level ($Z=1.96$), a 5% margin of error ($e=0.05$), and $p=0.5$. With 308 participants in the study, this number was exceeded, and the sample size obtained was found to be statistically sufficient.

Data collection

The research data were collected by the first researcher using a face-to-face survey method between December 2024 and March 2025. The researcher went to the classrooms before or after class hours and explained the purpose of the study. Students who volunteered to participate in the study were asked to fill out the Student Introduction Form, the Vocational Choices in Entering Nursing Scale (VCENS), and the Health Perception Scale (HPS). Data collection time was approximately 10-15 minutes.

Student Introduction Form

It consists of nine questions questioning students' age, gender,

grade, working status of mother and father, average monthly income, the most effective reason for choosing the nursing profession, satisfaction with the nursing profession, and the presence of nurses in the family/ relatives^{5,7}.

Vocational Choices in Entering Nursing Scale (VCENS)

The scale was developed by Zysberg and Berry to¹¹ determine the reason affecting nursing students' choice of vocation. The scale, the validity and reliability of which was carried out by Önlü and Saraçoğlu⁴, consists of 17 questions and two subscales, namely Vocational Congruency (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 9, 14, 15, 16, 17) and Survival Reasons (6, 8, 10, 11, 12, 13). Each item of the scale is rated in the range of 0% (not influential in my choice of vocation) to 100% (the most important factor in my choice of vocation) and the total scale and subscale scores are determined by dividing the total number of points given by the participants by the number of questions in the scale. Since the scale is not a diagnostic scale, the score ranges do not make any sense. According to the scores obtained from the scale, the reasons affecting the students' choice of nursing profession in terms of the independent variables examined are compared⁴. The Cronbach's alpha internal consistency coefficients of the scale and its subscales shown in Table 2.

Health Perception Scale (HPS)

The Health Perception Scale (HPS) was developed by Diamond et al. in 2007¹². HPS is a five-point Likert-type scale consisting of 15 items and four subscales (Centre of Control, Self-Awareness, Certainty and Importance of Health). The validity and reliability study of the scale was conducted by¹³. Items 1, 5, 9, 11 and 14 are positive statements; items 2, 4, 6, 8, 12, 13 and 15 are negative statements. Positive statements were scored as 'strongly agree=5', 'agree=4', 'undecided=3', 'disagree=2', 'strongly disagree=1'. Negative expressions were reverse scored. The minimum score that can be obtained from the scale is 15 and the maximum score is 75¹³. The Cronbach's alpha internal consistency coefficients of the scale and its subscales are shown in Table 2.

Data Analysis

The data obtained in the study were evaluated in computer environment through IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 22.0 (SPSS INC., Chicago, IL, USA) statistical programme. Frequency and percentage analyses were used to determine the descriptive characteristics of the students

participating in the study, and mean and standard deviation statistics were used to examine the scale. Kurtosis and Skewness values were analysed to determine whether the research variables were normally distributed. In there latered literature, the results of kurtosis and skewness values of the variables between +1.5 and -1.5¹⁴, +2.0 and -2.0¹⁵ are accepted as normal distribution. It was determined that the variables showed normal distribution. Parametric methods were used to analyse the data. The correlations between the scales and subscales were analysed with Pearson correlation test. Independent groups t-test, one-way analysis of variance (Anova) and post hoc (Tukey, LSD) analyses were used to examine the differences in scale levels according to the descriptive characteristics of the students.

Ethical Considerations

Before starting the study, ethical permission (Date: 18.12.2024 & No:13) was obtained from Hatay Mustafa Kemal University Non-Interventional Clinical Research Ethics Committee and institutional permission (Date: 21.11.2024 & No: E-40990652-200-444947) was obtained from Hatay Mustafa Kemal University Faculty of Health Sciences Dean's Office. In addition, the purpose of the study was explained to the students and their written/ verbal consent was obtained by informing them that participation in the study was voluntary. This research was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki.

RESULTS

Table 1. Distribution Of Descriptive Characteristics of The Students

Descriptive Characteristics		n	%
Gender	Female	204	66.2
	Male	104	33.8
Age	Under 20 years old	80	26.0
	Over 20 year sold	228	74.0
Class	1.	78	25.3
	2.	49	15.9
	3.	125	40.6
	4.	56	18.2
Mother's Employment Status	Working	58	18.8
	Not working	250	81.2
Father's Employment Status	Working	255	82.8
	Not working	53	17.2
Average Monthly Income of The Family	Minimum wage and below	50	16.2
	On the minimum wage	258	83.8
Satisfaction With The Nursing Department	Yes	191	62.0
	No	117	38.0
The Most Effective Reason For Choosing Nursing Profession*	Interest in the field of health	100	32.5
	Being easy to be appointed	151	49.0
	Being helpful	31	10.1
	Family request	26	8.4
Presence of A Nurse in The Family/ Relatives	Yes	180	58.4
	No	128	41.6
Mean Age Min:17 Max: 38	Mean±SD 20.64±1.95		

*:Only one option is marked

Of the student nurses who participated in the study, 66.2% were female, 74% were 20 years of age or older, 40.6% were in the 3rd grade, 81.2% of the mothers and 17.2% of the fathers were not working. It was determined that 83.8% of the student nurses had an income level above the minimum wage, 49% chose the nursing profession because it was easy to be appointed, 62% were satisfied with the nursing profession, 58.4% had nurses in their families or relatives, and the mean age was 20.64±1.95 years (Table 1).

Table 2. Scores of the Scale of Vocational Choices in Entering Nursing Scale and Health Perception Scale

	N	Mean	SD	Min.	Maks.	Kurtosis	Skewness	Alpha
VCENS Total	308	55.59	14.62	11.80	95.90	0.070	-0.195	0.82
Vocational Congruency	308	57.34	19.09	06.40	10.000	-0.384	-0.067	0.88
Survival Reasons	308	52.39	16.13	00.00	98.30	0.165	-0.098	0.53
HPS Total	308	50.67	6.94	34	70	-0.241	0.214	0.69
Center of Control	308	16.66	4.18	5	25	-0.265	-0.143	0.77
Self-Awareness	308	10.96	1.92	3	15	0.931	-0.213	0.42
Certainly	308	11.98	3.00	4	20	0.009	0,274	0.67
Importance of Health	308	11.06	2.17	5	15	-0.053	-0.401	0.55

The total VCENS, Vocational Congruency and Survival Centre of Control, Self-Awareness, Certainly and Importance Reasons subscales mean scores were 55.59 ± 14.62 , of Health subscales mean scores were 50.67 ± 6.94 , 16.66 ± 4.18 , 57.34 ± 19.09 and 52.39 ± 16.13 , respectively. The total HPS, 10.96 ± 1.92 , 11.98 ± 3.00 and 11.06 ± 2.17 , respectively (Table 2).

Table 3. Correlation Analysis Between Vocational Choices in Entering Nursing Scale and and Health Perception Scale

		VCENS Total	Vocational Congruency	Survival Reasons
HPS Total	r	0.095	0.086	-0.023
	p	0.096	0.133	0.682
Centre of Control	r	-0.065	-0.064	-0.088
	p	0.255	0.262	0.123
Self-Awareness	r	0.158**	0.179**	0.110
	p	0.005	0.002	0.053
Certainly	r	0.009	-0,001	-0.099
	p	0.875	0.987	0.084
Importance of Health	r	0.275**	0.239**	0.133*
	p	0.000	0.000	0.019

* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.001$; r: Pearson Correlation Analysis

A significant positive correlation was found between VCENS total, Vocational Congruency subscale and Self-Awareness subscale ($p < 0.05$). In addition, a significant positive correlation was determined between VCENS total, Vocational Congruency, Survival Reasons subscales and Importance of Health subscale ($p < 0.05$, $p < 0.001$) (Table 3).

It was determined that the VCENS total, Vocational Congruency and Survival Reasons subscales mean scores of the students who were satisfied with the nursing department were significantly higher than those who were not satisfied ($p < 0.05$, $p < 0.001$). A significant difference was determined between the most effective reason for choosing the nursing department and the means cores of VCENS total, Vocational Congruency subscale and Self-Awareness subscale ($p < 0.05$, $p < 0.001$). In the further analysis, it was determined that the significant difference was due to the fact that the mean scores of those who preferred the profession due to being interested in the field of health and being helpful were higher than those who preferred the profession due to the ease of appointment and family desire. No significant difference was found between the most effective reason for choosing the nursing department and the Survival Reasons subscale, and also between the mean scores of Vocational Congruency, Survival Reasons subscales and VCENS total scores with gender, class and the presence of nurses in the family/ relatives (Table 4).

Table 4. Comparison of VCENS Total and Subscale Score Means According to Descriptive Characteristics of Student Nurses

Demographic Characteristics	n	VCENS Total	Vocational Congruency	Survival Reasons
Gender		Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD
Female	204	55.78±14.61	55.78±19.46	53.69±1,514
Male	104	55.24±14.71	54.69±18.04	53.54±1,579
t=		0.307	0.478	0.081
p=		0.759	0.633	0.936
Class		Mean ± SD	Mean± SD	Mean ± SD
1.	78	58.21±12.89	56.17±18.02	56.81±12.84
2.	49	55.13±17.85	54.18±22.34	53.19±17.90
3.	125	54.26±15.01	54.79±18.57	53.28±15.82
4.	56	55.36±12.70	56.81±18.31	50.43±14.58
F=		1.200	0.255	1.987
p=		0.310	0.858	0.116
Satisfaction with the Nursing Department		Mean ± SD	Mean± SD	Mean ± SD
Yes	191	60.32±12.79	60.08±17.85	55.31±15.44
No	117	47.88±14.20	47.80±18.32	50.91±14.82
t=		7.942	5.802	2.464
p=		0.000**	0.000**	0.014*
Choosing a Profession Most Effective Cause		Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD	Mean± SD
Interest in the field of health ¹	100	59.05±14.06	58.71±20.37	52.26±15.94
Easy to Assign ²	151	53.37±14.36	52.84±17.28	55.19±14.73
Being Helpful ³	31	60.59±13.77	62.15±18.19	51.23±16.74
Family Request ⁴	26	49.28±15.13	49.62±20.23	52.88±14.58
F=		6.133	4.170	1.059
p=		0.000**	0.006*	0.367
Post Hoc=		1>2, 3>2, 1>4, 3>4 (p<0.05)	1>2, 3>2, 1>4, 3>4 (p<0.05)	
Family/ Relatives Nurse Presence		Mean± SD	Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD
Yes	180	55.25±14.92	55.41±19.14	52.82±15.64
No	128	56.09±14.24	55.41±18.79	54.79±14.87
t=		-0.494	0.003	-1.112
p=		0.622	0.997	0.267

*p<0.05; **p<0.001, F: Anova Test; t: Independent Groups T-Test; PostHoc: LSD

The mean scores of HPS total and Centre of Control subscale was significantly higher than those who were not satisfied of female students were significantly higher than those of male (p<0.05). A significant difference was found between the most students (p<0.05). A significant difference was found between effective reason for choosing the profession and HPS total and the grade level of the student nurses and the means cores of Self-Awareness subscale (p<0.05). According to the further HPS total (p<0.05), Centre of Control (p<0.001) and Certainly analysis, it is shown in the table that the significant difference (p<0.05) subscales. According to the further analysis, it is in the most effective reason for student nurses to choose the shown in the table that the significant difference in the class profession is due to which group score is higher. The mean level of the student nurses is caused by which group score is Self-Awareness score of the students who had nurses in their higher. The mean score of the Importance of Health subscale of families was found to be significantly higher than those who the students who were satisfied with the nursing department did not (Table 5).

Table 5. Comparison of HPS Total and Subscale Score Means According to Descriptive Characteristics of Student Nurses

Demographic Characteristics	n	HPS Total	Centre of Control	Self-Awereness	Certainly	Importance of Health
Gender		Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD	Mean± SD	Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD
Famele	204	51.33±6.83	17.03±4.04	11.05±1.79	12.07±3.03	11.16±2.14
Male	104	49.36±7.01	15.92±4.35	10.76±2.13	11.81±2.96	10.85±2.23
t=		2.375	2.230	1.252	0.706	1.185
p=		0.018*	0.026*	0.212	0.481	0.237
Class		Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD	Mean± SD	Mean ± SD
1.	78	52.29±6.30	18.25±3.40	10.70±2.02	12.52±3.10	10.80±2.27
2.	49	50.65±7.38	17.42±4.27	10.83±1.72	11.40±2.88	10.98±2.60
3.	125	49.40±6.95	15.42±4.35	11.24±1.93	11.61±2.86	11.12±2.08
4.	56	51.25±7.03	16.53±3.88	10.78±1.87	12.57±3.15	11.35±1.82
F=		2.985	8.597	1.624	2.824	0.748
p=		0.032*	0.000**	0.184	0.039*	0.524
PostHoc=		1>3 (p<0.05)	1>3, 2>3, 1>4 (p<0.05)		1>2, 4>2, 1>3, 4>3 (p<0.05)	
Satisfaction with the Nursing Department		Mean ± SD	Mean± SD	Mean± SD	Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD
Yes	191	50.49±6.38	16.33±3.84	10.84±1.72	12.02±3.06	11.28±1.92
No	117	50.96±7.79	17.19±4.63	11.14±2.20	11.93±2.93	10.69±2.50
t=		-0.580	-1.761	-1.319	0.252	2.345
p=		0.562	0.094	0.215	0.801	0.029*
Choosing a Profession Most Effective Cause		Mean± SD	Mean ± SD	Mean± SD	Mean± SD	Mean± SD
Interest in thefield of health ¹	100	50.52±7.05	16.56±4.11	10.73±1.77	12.03±3.06	11.20±2.05
EasytoAssign ²	151	49.76±6.68	16.39±4.17	10.83±2.00	11.68±2.90	10.85±2.18
Being Helpful ³	31	53.54±6.68	17.12±4.11	11.80±1.81	12.87±3.27	11.74±1.93
Family Request ⁴	26	53.07±7.21	18.07±4.44	11.57±1.79	12.50±2.95	10.92±2.75
F=		3.778	1.358	3.685	1.655	1.642
p=		0.011*	0.256	0.012*	0.177	0.180
PostHoc=		3>1, 3>2, 4>2 (p<0.05)		3>1, 4>1, 3>2 (p<0.05)		
Family/ Relatives Nurse Presence		Mean± SD	Mean± SD	Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD
Yes	180	51.23±6.99	16.86±4.35	11.17±1.83	12.02±2.88	11.17±2.07
No	128	49.87±6.82	16.37±3.92	10.65±2.00	11.93±3.18	10.90±2.31
t=		1.703	1.017	2.365	0.243	1.056
p=		0.090	0.310	0.019*	0.808	0.292

*p<0.05; **p<0.001, F: Anova Test; t: Independent Groups T-Test; PostHoc: Tukey, LSD

DISCUSSION

The total VCENS, Vocational Congruency and Survival Reasons subscales mean scores were 55.59 ± 14.62 , 57.34 ± 19.09 and 52.39 ± 16.13 , respectively. According to these averages, it can be thought that students find the nursing profession suitable for themselves and that survival reasons are also effective in choosing a profession at a similar rate. In parallel with our research results, it is seen that the average scores in the studies in the literature are close to each other and, as in the current study, higher scores were obtained from the Vocational Congruency subscale¹⁶⁻¹⁸.

Health perception is defined as the individual's evaluation of his/ her own health⁵. It is thought that nursing students' ability to evaluate their own health perceptions will positively affect their approach to individuals to whom they will provide health care services in the future and health management. In our study, the total HPS, Centre of Control, Self-Awareness, Certainly and Importance of Health subscales mean scores were 50.67 ± 6.94 , 16.66 ± 4.18 , 10.96 ± 1.92 , 11.98 ± 3.00 and 11.06 ± 2.17 , respectively. Considering that the highest score of 75 and the lowest score of 15 can be obtained from the scale, it can be said that the mean health perception scores of the students participating in the study are moderate. When the subscales of the scale are examined, it is seen that the subscale with the highest mean score is the centre of control subscale. Considering the studies conducted in the literature, it is concluded that the total mean score of the health perception scale of nursing students is at a medium level^{9,19}, and in other studies, respectively, the mean score of the health perception of the students is at a good level²⁰⁻²⁴.

In the study, it was found that student nurses who thought that they were suitable for the profession had higher self-awareness about their health and gave more importance to their health. Although studies examining the relationship between vocational choice and health perception are limited in the literature⁵, reported similar results in a study they conducted. Based on this result, it is thought that the future nurses who think that they are suitable for the nursing profession will have higher self-awareness of their own health and attach more importance to their health, which will have positive effects on the health of the individual, family and society.

Today, the choice of vocation is influenced by many factors such as personal characteristics, value judgements, interests, family expectations and the economic dimension of the profession. In this context, there are many factors for preferring the nursing profession^{8,25}. In our research, when the reasons for choosing the nursing profession are examined, it is concluded that students are mostly preferred because they are interested in the field of health and it is easy to be appointed. In parallel with our research results, in the studies conducted in the literature, among the reasons for preferring the nursing profession, it is preferred in terms of providing easy job opportunities^{5,6,17,26-35}, being able to help and care for people^{5,7,8,32,36-40}, loving the profession^{6,32,35,39}, with the influence of their close environment^{6,33-36,38}.

In our study, it was concluded that 62% of the students were satisfied with the nursing profession. Similar results were found in studies conducted with nursing students^{16,40-43}. Gender factor has a significant effect on health²³. In our study, when the total score and subscale means of HPS according to gender were examined, it was concluded that female students scored higher than male students. There are also some studies in the literature where no significant difference was found^{19,23,24}. It is thought that this difference in the study is due to the lower number of male students compared to female students.

In our study, a significant difference was found between the grade level of student nurses and the mean scores of HPS. In our study in which 1st and 4th graders had higher health perception, it is thought that 1st graders may have higher health perception scores because they have a young profile and have fewer chronic diseases, and 4th graders may have higher health perception scale scores considering the courses they take for health promotion behaviours.

In our study, a significant difference was found between the most effective reason for choosing the profession and the total and self-awareness subscale of the HPS. As the health perception of student nurses increases, their self-awareness levels increase and their self-confidence increases. Our study results give similar results with the studies examining the health perception of students in our country⁵.

The mean self-awareness score of students who had nurses in their families was found to be significantly higher than those who did not. When the literature was reviewed, no study examining the direct relationship with role models or professional motivation was found.

CONCLUSION

In our study, the main reasons for student nurses to choose the profession were the ease of appointment and interest in the field of health. Although it is sad that the nursing profession is preferred with the thought that it is easy to be appointed, the high number of those who are interested in the field is a pleasing situation for the profession. Awareness activities should be organised for the correct perception of the profession in the society and efforts should be made to promote the nursing profession. It was found that nursing students who thought that they were suitable for the profession had higher self-awareness about their health and gave more importance to their health. Thus, it is thought that when nurses with high self-awareness and giving importance to their health are trained, they will contribute to the development of individual, family and community health. Conducting these search with different variables in different sample groups and conducting qualitative research can contribute to the literature.

Limitation

The results cannot be generalized because only nursing students from one university were included in the study.

Funding information

No funding was received for this work.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Gönül Kara Söylemez: Conceptualization, Data curation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Supervision, Writing-original draft, Writing-review & editing.

Emine Çubukcu: Conceptualization, Data curation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Supervision, Writing-review & editing.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors confirm that no financial or personal relationships can lead to a conflict of interest regarding this study.

Acknowledgements

We extend our sincere gratitude to all the students who participated in this study.

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